

D5.2

Initial Data Management Plan

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CyberSecurity Hub	CSH	Czechia
National Cyber and Information Security Agency	NCISA	Czechia
South Moravian Innovation Centre	JIC	Czechia
Estonian Information Security Association	EISA	Estonia

Abbreviations

CA – Challenge Area
CHESS – Cyber-security Excellence Hub in Estonia and South Moravia
DMP – Data Management Plan
ICT – information and communication technology
KPI – key performance indicator
NGO – non-governmental organisation
R&I – Research and Innovation
TA – target audience
WP – work package
CVEs – Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures
MPC – multiparty computation
F4SLE – Framework for Security Level Evaluation

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1 Introduction

1.1 CHESS in short¹:

The Cybersecurity Excellence Hub in Estonia and South Moravia (CHESS) brings together leading R&I institutions in both regions to build connected innovation ecosystems to address one of the most important issues confronting Europe today: Cybersecurity.

The CHESS Hub has been designed specifically to meet the Cybersecurity challenges, building two linked Hubs in Estonia and South Moravia (Czech Republic), two regions that have already become important centres of IT industry and research. We develop a joint strategy closely aligned with the priorities set by the H2020 flagship cybersecurity pilot projects.

Our place-based ecosystems identify research and training needs and execute small pilot research projects as proofs of concept or to otherwise validate technologies or their business models. We seek to bridge the research-innovation gap by connecting fundamental researchers with economic and societal exploitation. CHESS seeks to leverage local and regional resources to support the development and sustainability of the ecosystem.

Project Objectives:

- Develop a cross-border joint cybersecurity research and innovation (R&I) strategy aligned with Czechian and Estonian smart specialisation strategies and Europe's digital society and cybersecurity goals.
- Apply the strategy in six focus areas of cybersecurity, i.e., six Challenge Areas:
 - Internet of Safe Things
 - Security Certification
 - Verification of Trustworthy Software
 - Security Preservation in Blockchain Technology
 - Post-Quantum Cryptography
 - Human-Centric Aspects of Security
- Initiate at least 12 small-scale R&I projects consolidating academia business linkages, demonstrate the validity of ideas, and provide evidence to obtain additional investments.
- Develop a training strategy for both regions to increase cross-border/sectoral cooperation and skills around the six priority areas.
- Raise visibility, citizen engagement, technology transfer, entrepreneurship training, staff exchange, and mutual learning in Cyber-Security.

1.2 Organisation of the CHESS project:

The CHESS project is organised in 5 WPs:

WP1

In WP1, we plan to analyse the existing state of the Cybersecurity Ecosystem in Estonia and South Moravia. The 6 CHESS Thematic Working group will help map out the capacities, expertise, common interests and needs in both regions. The mapping will take the form of *questionnaires* and *guided interviews*. The mapping exercise will help identify relevant stakeholders (companies and other actors in the regions). Based on the outcomes

¹ Extracts from the project website <https://chess-eu.cs.ut.ee/>

	<p>of the mapping exercise, the consortium will prepare the strategy to promote the excellence and impact of cybersecurity R&I in South Moravia and Estonia. The work done within this WP will result in <i>Strategic documents, i.e., public project deliverables</i>.</p> <p>Raw data from the mapping will not be published.</p>
WP2	<p>In this WP, we organise training and skills-building activities for ecosystem actors and provide excellent training open to global audiences. The project partners will create <i>training materials, presentations from workshops/seminars, and video recordings</i>, most of which will be publicly available on the CHESS website. Some training might have limited access, e.g., very specialised training for some project partners.</p>
WP3	<p>Small-scale R&I actions (12–24 months) will be implemented under WP3, supporting cross-regional integration and strategy building in CHESS's six diverse challenge areas. The focus of the R&I actions will be determined through the annual meetings. After these small-scale R&I actions (mini projects) are approved by the Strategy Board, they work independently of each other. They are led by different partners and have a very diverse focus. We will update DMP regularly to reflect the new research focus of the individual mini projects. We will publish reports about these R&I actions on the CHESS website. The WP3 activities will result in publications, Master theses, Open-source implementations, and joint presentations of the results.</p>
WP4	<p>Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication strategies are described in <i>D4.1 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan</i> of the CHESS project.</p>
WP5	<p>MUNI, responsible for WP5 Project Management, has established an electronic project monitoring workspace to keep all documents common to the project available to all partners. This space serves as an online working space for the partners and storage of all internal documents.</p>

1.3 CHESS Challenge Areas

CHESS Challenge Areas (CA) are the cornerstone of the CHESS project activities. Most of the work done will be on the level of individual Challenge Areas. Thematic working groups from each Challenge Area contribute to Strategy Development (WP1), Skills development actions and training (WP2), Research and Innovation (WP3) and Dissemination and communication (WP4).

CA1: Internet of Secure Things

Strategic Priorities

- Promote effective approaches that public and private organisations can take to support transition to and securely manage of IoST systems. Develop, validate and deploy IoST systems in various sectors, such as transportation.
- Improve security of IoST systems with advanced technologies.

Pilot research:

- Empirical Research on Security and Privacy Management in Intelligent Infrastructure Systems Analysis of Security-aware
- Privacy-preserving Smart Parking Solutions
- Secure and Privacy-preserving Access to Sharing Vehicles in Smart Cities

CA2: Security Certification

Strategic priorities

- Develop lightweight and automated (re)certification processes to ensure scalability.
- Explain vulnerabilities in certified devices by structuring certification documents that could be easily (deterministically) processed in an automated fashion to enable linkage of certification data to new knowledge regarding vulnerabilities within certified devices (CVEs, etc.)
- Develop methods of cybersecurity certification and deployment that ensure all layers and threats are correctly weighted. Cross-referencing certified items to vulnerability databases, like common vulnerabilities and exposures (CVEs)
- Develop security certification labels for devices, software and organisations that provide a simple and unambiguous depiction of the level(s) of the security being certified.

Pilot Research

- Enriching Certification Report Analysis with other Open-Source Intelligence
- Testing and improving a Method for Evaluating Organisations' Information Security

CA3: Verification of Trustworthy Software

Strategic Priorities

- Make use of Program Analysis Techniques to improve Software Development.
- Develop a theory of composable cybersecurity protocols to offer visual accounts of organisational cybersecurity protocols understandable to non-experts.
- Identify practically motivated challenges for basic research not yet covered by existing methodologies.

Pilot Research

- Development of Theory and Tool Support for Cybersecurity Protocols.
- Emerging problems in formal methods

CA4: Security Preservation in Blockchain

Strategic Priority

- Illustrate the state-of-the-art use of blockchain in vehicular communication environment.
- Develop building blocks for hardware wallets with multiparty computation (MPC).
- Demonstrate that blockchain can be used to manage traffic signals for emergency vehicles.

Pilot Research

- Secure consensus for Intelligent Vehicular Communication.
- Emergency Information transmission using blockchain in Intelligent Vehicular Communication.
- Blockchain-related operation protected by cryptographic hardware with MPC.

CA5: Post-Quantum Cryptography

Strategic Priority

- Evaluate the current state and practical applicability of post-quantum technologies.
- Assess usability & market viability of information security products based on post-quantum algorithms.

Pilot Research

- Evaluation of classical asymmetric algorithms (signatures, Diffie-Helman Key exchange, etc.) replaced by post-quantum algorithms (such as CRYSTALS-Dilithium and Kyber).
- Update and test the UXP data exchange layer (an electronic voting solution) with PQ.

CA6: Human-centric Aspects of Security

Strategic Priority

- Improve automated feedback systems for cybersecurity training.
- Improve usability of cybersecurity solutions for ICT professionals.

Pilot Research

- Evaluate Automated Feedback upgrade to KYPO Cyber Range Platform (an open-source interactive learning environment for hands-on cybersecurity training).
- Identify and address gaps in the usability of penetration testing reports among ICT professionals.

1.4 Data Management Principles

- The Coordinator will cooperate closely with Masaryk University's relevant professional services, i.e., the MUNI Open Science team, Open Science Methodologist at the Faculty of Informatics and MUNI Personal Data Protection Office.
- Personal data processing in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). This will apply to all surveys, questionnaires or interviews (e.g., mapping in WP1) to safeguard participants' anonymity. More information on standard procedures for processing personal data at Masaryk University can be found here: <https://www.muni.cz/en/about-us/official-notice-board/personal-data-protection>
- We will work in compliance with MUNI Open Science Strategy 2022–2028: <https://openscience.muni.cz/media/3477939/en-a-strategicka-cast-strategie-open-science-mu-2022-2028-uprprebal.pdf>
- The Data Management Plan (DMP) will be updated once a year or whenever a significant change may occur.
- Data Management will be on the agenda of Strategy Board meetings (will be regularly reviewed).
- CYBER is ISO/IEC 27001 and ISO 9001 certified. As such, CYBER has an ISMS (Information security management system) that dictates the rules for data management among other things. Hence, the users have to either work on data kept in the internal servers with nightly backups or back up their computers in the internal back-up server.

2 Data Summary

2.1 Re-Use of Existing Data

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

Challenge Areas will re-use different types of existing data. For open-source implementation (e.g., prototype, demonstration), we will use open-source code. We plan to use existing open-source projects in the form of software and libraries. We will use these components to build post-quantum systems (in CA5 Post-Quantum Cryptography). We will also use Common Criteria and FIPS 140 certification documents and accompanying documentation (all public) and NIST National Vulnerability Database. When preparing the Strategy within WP1, we plan to work with reports and policy documents published by various authorities and institutions. We might also benefit from different training materials produced in training projects or courses when preparing training events within WP2.

2.2 Data Types and Formats

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

The CHESS project will work only with well-known standard formats. Publications are typically PDF files that might be supported the raw data. Master theses (textual, graphical) may include source code in case of prototypes and demonstrations. Regarding open-source implementations, the consortium will work with repositories with a Docker container/GitLab repository, source code files, and related documentation. Survey results and benchmark results will be in tabular format. Other formats used will include PPTX, JSON, text documents and video format. Some of the Challenge Areas will generate data mainly in the form of publications and software. The re-used data then includes predominantly code.

2.3 The Purpose of Re-Used/Generated Data

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Based on the information we collect during the mapping/preparation of the SWOT analysis in WP1, we will identify and enable actions that will reinforce R&I excellence in the regions and promote the impact of cybersecurity R&I in diverse sectors of society and the economy. WP2 and data generated (training materials, video recordings, presentations) aim to increase the needed skills of the relevant stakeholders and target groups on cybersecurity issues. Generated publications support the project's key objective of cybersecurity education and raising awareness in all three ecosystems: academic, business and public ("triple helix"). The purpose of re-used or generated data within the CHESS project is project demonstrations, scientific research, and results of the small-scale projects that can be further used by different stakeholders. For example, in one of the activities, we create novel data about relations between standardisation documents and vulnerabilities. In another activity, we collect survey responses and provide their mutual comparisons.

2.4 Size of Data

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

We do not expect any significant size of the data to be generated or re-used within the projects (GBs). In some of the Challenge Areas, no datasets are planned to be produced, only publications and software. Therefore, there are no special requirements for data storage within the project.

2.5 Origin of Data

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

Some of the data is publicly available (e.g., open-source data in the form of publications and code). Part of the data will be collected from survey responders, e.g., data collected from organisations. For Master theses/publications/presentations, we will use literature analysis, analytical research, and validation of the research results. Project partners will develop open-source implementation using analytical research and validation of research results.

2.6 Data Utility Outside of the Project

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The data generated within the project might be useful to the scientific community, companies, the public, project partners, non-governmental institutions, security experts and managers. All publications aim to inform and educate actors from all four ecosystems (quadruple helix). Any software(s) shall be reusable for future research.

3 Fair data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Data generated within the project will be identified by a persistent identifier. Publications will be assigned standard identifiers, mostly DOI. Code will be assigned identifiers given by the repositories, mainly GitHub, GitLab, etc. Some of the open-source implementations will be identified by Project ID on GitHub. Theses are published in repositories of the relevant institution (e.g., MUNI theses are published in the nationwide repository and are assigned persistent URLs). Data from one of the mini project (seccerts in CA2 <https://seccerts.org/>) will be available with a persistent identifier in incremental versions. Statistics and results of analyses from another mini project (Framework for Security Level Evaluation F4SLE survey) will be available in the form of publications (with a persistent identifier) and presentations. We also plan to use Zenodo communities to ensure all our research outputs have a persistent identifier, persistent storage, and common collection gathering all outputs of the project.

3.1.2 Metadata and Their Standards

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Most metadata will be made available through the project deliverables and open-access publications, as well as through the project dissemination channels (e.g., project website and social media accounts). Standard metadata collected and published by scientific databases and code repositories will be provided. For all results deposited in Zenodo, it will be possible to export their metadata in standard formats such as MARCXML, Dublin Core and DataCite Metadata Schema (by means of the repository itself). The type of metadata depends on the specific activity and project output. For example, in one activity, metadata about relations of standards and other documents examined is the actual output of the activity:

- Protection profile (PP): PP Title, PP Version, the target of evaluation, Evaluation Assurance Level, CC Version, PP Author.

Some of the other metadata include:

- Master Theses: authors name, abstract, graduation thesis language, graduation thesis type, supervisor(s), defence year, keywords.
- Publications: depends on the publisher.
- Presentations and video demonstration: author, title, short abstract, keywords.
- Benchmarks: author, title, explanation of dataset structure.

The issue of metadata and their standards will be further specified in the next version of DMP depending on the progress and research focus of individual Challenge Areas.

3.1.3 Keywords

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimise the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Search keywords will be provided in the metadata. Target publication venues are open-access peer-reviewed journals and conferences due to vast dissemination opportunities. The publication venues are easy to access online and offer a simple keyword, author, or DOI (digital object identifier) search through their homepages or publication search engines such as "sciencedirect.com" or "scopus.com". In addition, references will be made via the project's official website. The keywords will be provided for Master theses, publications, video demonstrations, benchmark results and code.

3.1.4 Providing Metadata for Indexing

Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Publications (and relevant metadata) will be indexed in scientific libraries (such as SCOPUS, WoS, ScienceDirect, IEEExplore) and software will be indexed in open-source repositories (mainly GitHub and GitLab). For all results deposited in Zenodo, their metadata will be exported via OAI-PMH and will allow for harvesting (by means of the repository itself).

3.2 Making data accessible

Repository:

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

The consortium will use the official institutional repositories of the partners. For open-source implementation, these will be institutional installations of Github/GitLab, e.g. <https://gitlab.cs.ut.ee/>, <https://github.com/crocs-muni/>. For theses, we will use official university registries, e.g. <https://is.muni.cz/thesis/> or https://comserv.cs.ut.ee/ati_thesis/index.php?language=et. Research and survey papers produced will be published as open-access by taking up self-archiving rights for journals and conferences that have them, or if necessary, paying the open-access fees where self-archiving and or free open access is not possible. Some examples of free repositories we plan to use include <https://www.iacr.org/eprint/> or <https://arxiv.org/>. All final versions of publications will be stored in correspondence with journal/conference open access rules at several public repositories such as university libraries, ResearchGate or other open libraries. We will use Zenodo communities (as mentioned above). The project website will also serve as a repository for project outputs, such as publications, training materials, video recordings or presentations.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

The repositories mentioned above have been used in the past without any objections and provide safe and long-lasting storage.

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

The publication and theses repositories ensure that data is assigned an identifier, i.e., DOI, ISSN, ISBN for publications. We plan to use Zenodo communities for other research outputs, e.g., project deliverables.

Data:

Will all data be made openly available?

All data will be made openly available apart from survey data. The survey input data/raw data can be accessed only by the project partner(s) who provided or collected it, as the data contains sensitive organisational data.

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

N/A

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?

All repositories we plan to use are accessible through HTTPS protocol.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

In some cases, there are closed thesis defences, and there might be restrictions on access depending on the thesis license. Regarding surveys, only aggregated results will be provided to the project deliverables.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

N/A

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g., to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

N/A

Metadata:

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Yes, metadata will be openly available.

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

All repositories we plan to use provide long-term storage of data. Both data and metadata will remain available for at least ten years after the project end date or as long as needed.

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g., in open source code)?

Data generated within the project will be in standard formats and no additional software will be needed to access or read the data. Publications will be open-access, and software will be published as open-source. The same applies to metadata.

3.3 Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

The consortium will use open data formats (common, well-known formats only) that are easily usable and will make it easy for anyone interested in working with the data. Publications and theses will be available in standard formats; PDF is expected. Source code will be available through standard repositories in open-text format.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

N/A

Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

Our data will include qualified references to other data where appropriate. The open-source implementations will typically use (reference) the available libraries and other open-source implementations.

3.4 Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)? Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Our data will be freely available in order to permit the widest re-use possible (apart from sensitive/raw data from surveys). All data will be available in trusted repositories (see above) and on the project website. Our data will be licensed using free licenses. Publications will be open access. For open-source implementations, readme files and related publications will be available.

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes, as almost all of the results of the project will be accessible in respective/above mentioned repositories, with permissive licences, the data produced will be usable by third parties also after the end of the project.

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Yes, where appropriate. For example, for open-source implementations, the provenance of the data will be documented through the commit tracking in Git Repository.

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

We will follow the relevant data quality assurance processes according to the applicable standards.

- Survey results: Checking the data entries on completeness and general correctness based on the open-access documents

- Theses are publicly defended at a university
- Open-source implementations: The developed implementations will be tested against the functional requirements and the design goals.
- The publications are reviewed by the international committees.

4 Other research outputs

All project outputs are described in the sections above.

5 Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ? How will these be covered?

There are no special costs expected for making data FAIR in our project. We use the standard services at the partner institutions. We need data specialists to support the consortium, but they are part of the standard service at the institutions, so they are not included in the project budget.

We expect only costs related to open-access conferences and journal fees for produced publications. The cost for OA publishing is included in the project budget.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project? How will long-term preservation be ensured?

Challenge Area Leads are responsible for data management within their area. They monitor progress and data management within individual mini projects. CA Leads are supported by the Project Coordinator and Open Science Team at Masaryk University and the institution they come from. All repositories we plan to use provide long-term storage of data. Both data and metadata will remain available for at least ten years after the project end date or as long as needed (see above).

6 Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

All data will be stored on the institutional storage infrastructures and automatically backed up. As the CHESS consortium is focused on cybersecurity, and includes many data security and IT experts, we are confident that the project data is and will be well secured. For example, Cybersecurity Team of Masaryk University CSIRT-MU is the first certified cybersecurity team in the Czech Republic. Their main focus is to protect cyberspace at Masaryk University.

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes, the data will be safely stored in trusted repositories mentioned above.

7 Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

According to the Grant Agreement, any research connected to the CHESS project will be carried out in compliance with fundamental ethical principles. If we identify an ethical issue, we will approach an ethical committee at a relevant institution to get approval and proceed according to standard procedures and regulations.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

We will follow GDPR standard procedures (see above).

8 Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

The project is a cooperation of many independent mini projects, where the type of data differs and will change as the project progresses. This Initial DMP describes the data we are aware of at the moment. The consortium plans to update the DMP regularly (at least once a year) to reflect changes within individual Challenge Areas and mini projects. The next update might be the collection of data management plans for individual Challenge Areas if the Strategy Board finds this beneficial.